

FUNCTIONS OF LEXICAL STYLISTIC DEVICES HYPERBOLE

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Abstract

The purposes of hyperbole as a lexical stylistic device in literature and ordinary speech are examined in this article. Deliberate exaggeration for emphasis or impact is known as hyperbole, and it can be used to create vivid images, increase emotional intensity, and promote humor, among other things.

Keywords: Hyperbole, stylistic device, discussion, improvement, novel, experience, inversion.

The audience is not expected to accept that this character actually killed a bear when he was "only three" or that he knew "every tree." Rather, Davy Crockett's frontier experience is exaggerated and made to seem larger than life through the use of hyperbole. In tall tales, folklore, and folk tales, hyperbole is a common literary device. The audience is aware that these assertions are meant to highlight the characters' qualities rather than to be accepted literally. Overstatement and hyperbole can be synonyms for one another and are frequently used interchangeably. Hyperbole and overstatement, however, differ slightly in how they are used and what they are meant to accomplish. An exaggeration or a statement that goes beyond what most people would find realistic is called an overstatement [1;9].

A hyperbole is also an exaggeration, yet it is often more extreme than an overstatement and its intended effect is as a literary or rhetorical device. Both overstatement and hyperbole are figures of speech and are not meant to be understood literally. Hyperbole, however, is utilized as a device in literature and rhetoric, not just a form of figurative language. Why hyperbola? They release and release the educator from the circle of truth. Hyperbole plays an important role in literature because it invigorates our speech and gives us an emotional and mental state as the author or narrator of the text. This gives them the opportunity to present the oral environment of the story clearly and correctly. Hyperbole device function-to give brightness, emotionality and reliability to the text. In addition, he often works by humorous writers to create satirical images for the heroes of his works, which gives the reader the opportunity to return his imagination to life in his imagination. The task of "finding Hyperbola in the text" is very simple, because speech among others turns into pronounced syllables, which are distinguished by the fact that they exist. Examples of use: "the eyes of this girl were surprised by the size of a saucer" or "this dog was the size of an elephant". All these phrases are a visible addition of reality, because you do not meet such a girl on the street big eyes or a dog of the size of an elephant, because

in nature they are not and cannot be either. These are the most simple examples using a stylistic tool, which is considered in the language of Russian literature. Metaphor and hyperbole are commonly used literary devices. A writer uses metaphor to compare things with some other persons or things. At times, it is an unusual comparison. Sometimes it seems overstatement which is not meant normally. In the case of hyperbole, it is different because its usage is meant to exaggerate and not take the thing or idea literally. The statement that his words are music could be an overstatement but not always. Hence it is a metaphor. However, to say that his words are the greatest melody that was ever heard is an exaggeration and this is hyperbole, which is always meant to exaggerate things. As hyperbole is meant to overstate and exaggerate things, it is also meant to bring humor. Therefore, using hyperbole in satire makes things or ideas or persons larger than life or lesser than life with exaggeration or even understatement [2;56].

Hyperbole is effective as a literary device in many ways. By exaggerating something in an extreme way, whether it is a character's traits, writer's tone, theme, or idea, hyperbole can capture a reader's attention. In addition, it can cause the reader to question a narrator's reliability, reflect on the writer's true intention, or provide a level of absurd humor for entertainment. Swift's satirical essay reflects his view of the oppressive policies and attitudes toward Ireland and the poor on the part of the British people and overall aristocracy in the early eighteenth century. This is one of the most famous hyperbolic passages in literature, as Swift suggests selling and using Irish children as a food source to relieve the economic plight of the Irish people. Of course, this "proposal" is a figure of speech and intended as an extreme exaggeration rather than a literal solution. However, the practical and almost casual tone with which Swift delivers his hyperbole is as shocking for readers as what he appears to be suggesting. As a literary and rhetorical device in the essay, hyperbole achieves a serious and ironic effect for the reader. We can say everything classical works rely on the transmission of the author's feelings to the reader, transferring it to the situation in which he himself created it. In literature, hyperbole classical works were very actively used by many famous authors. Artistic expression, rich in literary means, will help these authors the best way to express their opinion to the reader. Thus, when studying the works of Classics, students are looking for epithets, comparisons, personification, and try to understand why the writer used this or that technique. Among the artistic means hyperbole also applies, we will consider. Consider what Hyperbola is, its examples are presented below. This is a special deliberate exaggeration, which allows the author to achieve the desired effect. This term is very ancient, the technique began to be used in ancient times [3;31].

Use for hyperbole expression language means: words, word combinations and sentences. The simplest examples: Hyperbola is widely used in Russian. Examples show that we often use this technique without even paying attention to it. For example, quote; "I told you a thousand times!" In this case, "a thousand times" is an exaggeration, because the author of the statement, first of all, many times did not say anything. Secondly, he did not calculate the number of repetitions. Another example of hyperbole in Russian: "We have not seen each other for a hundred years." People who come here have not met for a long time, but certainly for a hundred years. Saying that he has millions of problems, the man now claims that he has a black line in his life, and there cannot be said about the exact quantitative definition of problems. Satirists often rely on hyperbole to emphasize a point and focus a reader's attention on a socio-political or economic problem. Unfortunately, there were people in Swift's time that made a literal interpretation of his modest proposal. This caused a backlash among certain members of the aristocracy due to their misunderstanding of his hyperbole. However, for a modern audience, rather than discounting Swift's essay as something ridiculous, his hyperbolic proposal achieves its intended effect by causing the reader to reflect on the underlying problems that would result in such a dramatic literary essay—both in Swift's time and today [4].

In conclusion, we examined instances of hyperbole and its application by word masters. By utilizing this style, authors can make their discourse expressive and figurative, drawing the reader's attention to any aspect of the person or thing being described. Furthermore, the author used purposeful exaggeration to convey his perspective on the events.

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